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Evaluation of some Bio-pesticides against some Important Lepidopteron Pests of Pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* L.) at Pantnagar, Uttarakhand, India

Jaba Jagdish*, Meena Agnihotri and Rakesh Sharma

Department of Entomology, GBPUAT, Pantnagar, Uttarakhand, India.

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*Corresponding Author

Jaba Jagdish

E-mail: jaba.jagdish@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

The field experiment conducted to evaluate the relative efficacy of eight biopesticides against gram pod borer *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hubner), legume pod borer, *Maruca vitrata* (Geyer) and *E. zinkenella* infesting Pigeonpea during Kharif season 2010. The population was recorded at different days after spraying of insecticides and it was found that the number of larvae varied non-significantly different from the control in both spray application. Significant effect of biopesticides on percent webbing by *M. vitrata*, at First spray application showed minimum (32.00/25shoots) in NSKE 5.0 % @ 50 g/lit. The pod borer *M. vitrata* was found lowest in Spinosad 45%ww @73g.ai/ha (4.50%), followed by NSKE 5 % (4.81%) and *B. bassiana* DOR SC @ 1.89gm/lit (5.39%) as compared to control (14.49%). The percent pod damage by *H. armigera* varied significantly which was minimum (27.84%) in Spinosad 45%ww @73g.ai/ha followed by *B. bassiana* WP @ 1.5kg/ha (28.58%) and *B. bassiana* DOR SC @ 1.89gm/lit (28.73%) in comparison to control (51.68%). Grain yield varied from maximum of 1200 kg/ha in Spinosad 45%ww @73g.ai/ha followed by 1191.67 kg/ha in *B. bassiana* DOR SC @ 1.89gm/lit as compared to 708.33kg/ha in untreated control.

INTRODUCTION

Pigeonpea (*Cajanus cajan* L.) is a tropical grain legume mainly grown in India and ranks second in area and production, and contribute about 90% of the world's pulse production. In India, pigeonpea is grown in 4.42 million ha with an annual production of 2.89 million tonnes and 655 kg ha⁻¹ of productivity. It is attacked by more than 250 species of insects, of which gram pod borer, *Helicoverpa armigera* and legume pod borer or spotted pod borer, *Maruca vitrata* are the most important polyphagous pests in both tropics and sub-tropics because of their extensive host range, destructiveness and distribution on cowpea, mungbean, urdbean and field bean (Shanower *et al.*, 1999). *Helicoverpa* causes heavy loss up to 60% with an annual loss estimated to be US \$ 400 million in pigeonpea (Anonymous, 2007). The loss caused due to *Maruca* was estimated to be about 84 percent (Dharmasena *et al.*, 1992) accounting to US \$ 30 million (Saxena *et al.*, 2002). *Maruca* is basically a hidden pest and completes its larval development inside the web formed by rolling and tying together leaves, flowers, buds and pods. This typical concealed feeding protects the larvae from natural enemies, human interventions or other adverse factors including insecticides (Sharma, 1998). It is essential to kill the first instar larvae during the period when they hatch till they enter the flowers and buds. Management of pod borer complex in pigeonpea relies heavily on insecticides, often to the exclusion of other methods of control. Considerable numbers of insecticides have been tested and few of them found effective against the pod borers in pigeonpea (Yadav and Dahiya, 2004). Reports of high level of resistance to the conventional insecticides in *H. armigera* have resulted in renewed interest in the research for exploring the opportunities of using biopesticides. Biopesticides such as *Bacillus thuringiensis* (Berliner) (Bt), *Beauveria bassiana*, NSKE 5% etc. can provide an alternative, more environmentally friendly option to control these insect pests (Jeyarani and Karuppuchamy, 2010). Keeping in view, the present study was undertaken to evaluate the bio efficacy of certain biopesticides against the pod borers in pigeonpea ecosystem.

MATERIALS & METHODS

$$\text{Per cent pod damage} = \frac{\text{Number of damaged pods} \times 100}{\text{Total number of pods}}$$

Observations on grain yield

The grain yield of different treatments was obtained by harvesting the central rows after leaving the border

The experiments were carried out under field conditions at the Norman Borlague crop research center, GBPUAT, Pantnagar, Uttarakhand, India during Kharif from June to December 2010 on Pigeonpea variety 'UPAS-120' in randomized complete block design (RBD) having nine treatments replicated thrice with each plot consisted of 30 m² (10 rows of 5m, each at 60 cm spacing). To study the efficiency of various bio-pesticides against *M. vitrata*, *Helicoverpa armigera* and *E. zinkenella* on the Pigeonpea were used in each trial. The trial had eight bio-pesticides viz., *B. bassiana* DOR SC formulation @ 1.89gm/lit *B. bassiana* WP @ 1.5 kg/ha, NSKE 5.0 % @ 50 gm/lit, combination of Bt + *B. bassiana* (DOR) @ 2.5 gm/lit, Combination of Bt + *B. bassiana* (DOR) @ 3.0 gm/lit, Commercial Bt formulation @ 1.5 kg/ha, Spinosad 45 % WW @ 73 g ai/ha and control plot. The following observation will be made.

Observations on the effect of bio-pesticides on major insect pests of pigeonpea

The larval population of *M. vitrata*, *H. armigera*, *E. zinkenella* and percent webbing by *M. vitrata* were observed by selecting 25 shoots from each plot and the larval population of *H. armigera* were observed on pre tagged 5 plants from each plot. Observations were taken at the first day before the third, seventh and tenth days after each spray.

Observations on pod damage at maturity

Pod damage at maturity of the crop was recorded from pods of 16 plants per plot at random in each plot. Sample pods were examined for the damage of major pod borers viz. *H. armigera* and *M. vitrata*.

To differentiate damage of these pod borers the following criteria were adopted according to Yadav *et al.* (1988).

1. Healthy clear pods without any external damage symptom.
2. Pods attacked by *H. armigera* having big circular holes without larvae exuviae's on the pods.
3. Pods attacked by *M. vitrata* having relatively small holes with scrapped margins, plugging of entrance hole with larval excreta.

Besides, above total number of pods and number of damaged pods by various pod borers were recorded separately for each sample and converted into percent pod damage as indicated below:

rows on each side at maturity. After harvesting the grains were dried in open sunlight to stabilize the moisture content. The weight of grain of sample and plot was taken after this period. The total yield per

plot included in the yield of sample grains and it was then computed on kg per ha basis.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The data recorded on larval population of *H. armigera*, *M. vitrata*, *Eteilla* and per cent webbing by *M. vitrata* before first spray, 3 Days After First Spray (DAFS), 7 DAFS and 10 DAFS (Table 1).

Pre-treatment counts on larval population of *H. armigera*, *M. vitrata*, *Eteilla* before application of the treatment showed that there were 0.33-33, 12.33-23, 0.33-1.33 larvae per 25 shoots, respectively. However, percent webbing by *M. vitrata* before application of the treatments showed that there was 44-100% per 25 shoots.

The population dynamics of *H. armigera*, *M. vitrata* and *E. zinkenella* were recorded at different days after spraying of insecticides and it was found that the number of larvae varied non-significantly different from the control in both spray application (Table 1A and 1B). However, there was significant effect of bio-pesticides on percent webbing by *M. vitrata*, and *H. armigera* at First spray application was varied from minimum (32.00/25shoots) in NSKE 5.0 % @ 50gm/lit to maximum (61.33/25shoots) in both Commercial Bt formulation @ 1.5 kg/ha and Spinosad 45 % WW @ 73 g ai/ha in comparison to control (69.33/25shoots).

The data recorded on percent pod damage due to *M. vitrata* and *H. armigera* is presented in (Table 1C). The percent pod damage due to *M. vitrata* and *H. armigera* showed significant differences among treatments. In case of *M. vitrata*, the Spinosad 45%ww @73g.ai/ha showed significantly reduced (4.50%) per cent pod damage followed by NSKE 5 % (4.81%) and

B. bassiana DOR SC @ 1.89gm/lit (5.39%) as compared to control (14.49%). In case *H. armigera* showed that per cent pod damage varied significantly from minimum (27.84%) in Spinosad 45%ww @73g.ai/ha followed by *B. bassiana* WP @ 1.5kg/ha(28.58%) and *B. bassiana* DOR SC @ 1.89gm/lit (28.73%) to maximum (42.48%) in Combination of Bt + *B. bassiana* (DOR) @ 2.5 gm/lit in comparison to control (51.68%). Grain yield varied from maximum of 1200 kg/ha in Spinosad 45%ww @73g.ai/ha followed by 1191.67 kg/ha in *B. bassiana* DOR SC @ 1.89gm/lit as compared to 708.33kg/ha in untreated control.

The results are in agreement with the findings of Rao *et al.* (2007) who reported that pod damage due to legume pod borer, *M. vitrata* was lowest in plants sprayed with spinosad and also registered lowest seed damage (3.9) and highest grain yield (795 kg/ha). Mittal and Ujagir (2005) reported that lower numbers of *H. armigera* and lower pod damage were recorded in spinosad 90g, spinosad 73g, spinosad 56g and spinosad 45g a.i/ha, compared to other standard insecticides and untreated control. Sreekanth and Seshamahalakshmi (2012) reported that pod damage due to *Maruca* was the lowest in spinosad (17.38%), followed by Bt.-1 (27.57%) and *B. bassiana* SC formulation @ 300 mg/lit (33.82%) as against control (45.84%) with 62.1, 39.9 and 26.2 percent reduction over control respectively. The highest grain yield was recorded in spinosad 45% SC @ 73 g.i/ha treated plots (831.0 kg/ha), followed by Bt.1 @ 1.5 kg/ha (743.1 kg/ha) and *B. bassiana* SC formulation @ 300mg/Lt (694.4 kg/ha) with 104.0, 82.4 and 70.5 percent increase over control respectively as against the minimum yield of 407.4 kg/ha in the untreated check.

Table 1A: Evaluation of different microbial insecticide against major lepidopteron pests of pigeonpea during 2010-11

SI No	Treatments	Preobservationbeforel spray No. Of insects/ 25 shoots*				3DAFS				7DAFS			
		<i>H. armigera</i>	<i>M. vitrata</i>	<i>Eteilla</i>	Webbing (%)	<i>H. armigera</i>	<i>M. vitrata</i>	<i>Eteilla</i>	Webbing (%)	<i>H. armigera</i>	<i>M. vitrata</i>	<i>Eteilla</i>	Webbing (%)
1	<i>B. bassiana</i> DOR SC formulation@1.89gm /lt	0.67 (1.05)	22.00 (4.70)	0.67 (4.47)	78.67 (67.03)	0.00 (0.71)	7.00 (2.71)	0.00 (0.71)	54.67 (47.68)	0.00 (0.71)	8.00 (2.83)	0.00 (0.71)	46.67 (42.71)
2	<i>B. bassiana</i> WP @. 1.0 kg/ha	0.67 (1.05)	12.33 (3.55)	1.00 (4.39)	44.00 (45.72)	0.00 (0.71)	6.33 (2.60)	0.00 (0.71)	41.33 (39.99)	0.00 (0.71)	5.00 (2.33)	0.00 (0.71)	40.00 (39.12)
3	<i>B. bassiana</i> WP @. 1.5 kg/ha	0.67 (1.05)	17.67 (4.26)	1.00 (5.33)	85.33 (67.99)	0.00 (0.71)	7.3 (2.69)	0.00 (0.71)	54.67 (47.92)	0.00 (0.71)	7.00 (2.72)	0.00 (0.71)	45.33 (42.30)
4	NSKE 5.0 % @ 50 gm/lit	33 (0.88)	19.00 (4.41)	1.00 (4.91)	45.33 (46.73)	0.00 (0.71)	8.00 (2.83)	0.00 (0.71)	52.00 (46.26)	0.00 (0.71)	3.67 (1.97)	0.00 (0.71)	32.00 (34.29)
5	Combination of Bt + <i>B. bassiana</i> (DOR) @ 2.5 gm/lit	0.33 (0.87)	16.33 (4.10)	1.33 (5.43)	85.33 (76.15)	0.00 (0.71)	11.67 (3.48)	0.00 (0.71)	62.67 (52.34)	0.00 (0.71)	6.00 (2.55)	0.33 (0.88)	38.67 (38.41)
6	Combination of Bt + <i>B. bassiana</i> (DOR) @ 3.0 gm/lit	0.33 (0.87)	23.00 (4.83)	0.33 (4.28)	72.00 (59.19)	0.00 (0.71)	8.67 (3.00)	0.33 (0.88)	58.67 (50.05)	0.00 (0.71)	6.67 (2.62)	0.33 (0.88)	42.67 (3.29)
7	Commercial Bt formulation @ 1.5 kg/ha	0.67 (1.05)	19.67 (4.47)	1.33 (5.17)	90.67 (79.35)	0.00 (0.71)	11.33 (3.43)	0.00 (0.71)	66.67 (54.85)	0.00 (0.71)	7.00 (2.64)	0.33 (0.88)	61.33 (3.95)
8	Spinosad 45 % WW @ 73 g ai/ha	0.33 (0.88)	18.00 (4.30)	0.33 (4.86)	100.00 (90.00)	0.00 (0.71)	10.33 (3.43)	0.00 (0.71)	61.33 (53.86)	0.00 (0.71)	7.67 (2.84)	0.33 (0.88)	61.33 (51.57)
9	Control	0.33 (0.88)	17.33 (4.20)	1.00 (4.67)	100.00 (90.00)	0.00 (0.71)	9.00 (3.25)	0.33 (0.88)	62.67 (54.62)	0.00 (0.71)	9.00 (3.02)	0.67 (1.05)	69.33 (56.41)
	SEM ±												(.52)
	CD at5%												(1.56)

DAFS= Days after first spray,* Data given in parentheses are Square root transformed values, ** Data given in parentheses are Angular transformed values

Table 1B: Evaluation of different microbials against Lepidopteron pests in pigeonpea

Treatments	Pre-observation on II spray No. Of insects/ 25 shoots *				3DASS No. of insects/ 25 shoots *				7DASS No. of insects/ 25 shoots *			
	<i>H. armigera</i>	<i>M. vitrata</i>	<i>Eteilla</i>	Webbing (%)	<i>H. armigera</i>	<i>M. vitrata</i>	<i>Eteilla</i>	Webbing (%)	<i>H. armigera</i>	<i>M. vitrata</i>	<i>Eteilla</i>	Webbing (%)
<i>B.bassiana</i> DOR SC formulation @1.89gm/lt	0.00 (0.71)	4.67 (2.27)	0.00 (0.71)	52.00 (46.16)	0.00 (0.71)	8.00 (2.83)	0.00 (0.71)	32.00 (34.36)	0.00 (0.71)	6.00 (2.54)	0.33 (0.88)	14.67 (22.01)
<i>B .bassiana</i> WP @. 1.0 kg/ha	0.00 (0.71)	3.67 (2.04)	0.67 (1.05)	41.33 (39.96)	0.00 (0.71)	7.33 (2.79)	0.00 (0.71)	40.00 (38.85)	0.00 (0.71)	5.67 (2.41)	0.00 (0.71)	17.33 (23.72)
<i>B. bassiana</i> WP @. 1.5 kg/ha	0.00 (0.71)	3.67 (2.00)	0.00 (.71)	44.00 (41.55)	0.00 (0.71)	7.67 (2.85)	0.00 (0.71)	48.00 (43.84)	0.00 (0.71)	6.33 (2.59)	0.00 (0.71)	16.00 (23.47)
NSKE 5.0 % @ 50 gm/lit	0.00 (0.71)	4.33 (2.16)	0.33 (0.88)	53.33 (46.90)	0.00 (0.71)	7.33 (2.78)	0.00 (0.71)	36.00 (36.82)	0.00 (0.71)	6.00 (2.54)	0.33 (0.88)	12.00 (20.09)
Combination of Bt + <i>B. bassiana</i> (DOR) @ 2.5 gm/lit	0.00 (0.71)	6.33 (2.60)	0.67 (1.05)	45.33 (42.29)	0.00 (0.71)	7.00 (2.72)	0.00 (0.71)	40.00 (39.16)	0.00 (0.71)	6.00 (2.52)	0.67 (1.05)	22.67 (28.29)
Combination of Bt + <i>B. bassiana</i> (DOR) @ 3.0 gm/lit	0.00 (0.71)	4.67 (2.24)	0.00 (0.71)	42.67 (40.77)	0.00 (0.71)	5.67 (2.47)	0.00 (0.71)	38.67 (38.08)	0.00 (0.71)	2.67 (1.74)	0.00 (0.71)	24.00 (28.82)
Commercial Bt formulation @ 1.5 kg/ha	0.00 (0.71)	8.33 (2.97)	1.00 (1.22)	54.67 (47.68)	0.00 (0.71)	7.00 (2.73)	0.00 (0.71)	40.00 (38.94)	0.00 (0.71)	5.67 (2.20)	0.00 (0.78)	20.00 (26.49)
Spinosad 45 % WW @ 73 gai/ha	0.00 (0.71)	5.00 (2.33)	0.33 (0.88)	48.00 (43.84)	0.00 (0.71)	6.00 (2.54)	0.00 (0.71)	32.00 (34.28)	0.00 (0.71)	4.33 (1.99)	0.00 (0.71)	24.00 (29.28)
control	0.00 (0.71)	3.67 (2.00)	0.33 (0.88)	57.33 (49.84)	0.00 (0.71)	9.00 (3.07)	0.00 (0.71)	50.67 (45.42)	0.00 (0.71)	5.67 (2.41)	0.67 (1.05)	26.67 (30.99)
SEM±	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
CD at 5%	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

DAFS= Days after first spray,* Data given in parentheses are Square root transformed values, ** Data given in parentheses are Angular transformed values

Table 1C: Evaluation of different microbials against Lepidopteron pests in pigeonpea

Sl.No.	Treatments	Pod Damage (%)		Yield(kg/ha)
		Pod Borer	<i>M. vitrata</i>	
1	<i>B. bassiana</i> DOR SC formulation @1.89gm/lt	5.39(13.38)	28.73(32.39)	1191.67
2	<i>B. bassiana</i> WP @. 1.0 kg/ha	9.36 (17.77)	38.90(38.58)	758.33
3	<i>B. bassiana</i> WP @. 1.5 kg/ha	7.92(16.24)	28.58(32.30)	783.33
4	NSKE 5.0 % @ 50 gm/lit	4.81(12.34)	29.87(32.96)	970.00
5	Combination of Bt + <i>B. bassiana</i> (DOR) @ 2.5 gm/lit	7.44(15.77)	42.48(40.67)	941.66
6	Combination of Bt + <i>B. bassiana</i> (DOR) @ 3.0 gm/lit	9.59(17.99)	34.09(35.68)	975.00
7	Commercial Bt formulation @ 1.5 kg/ha	6.77(14.73)	36.10(36.89)	1016.66
8	Spinosad 45 % WW @ 73 g a.i/ha	4.50(12.07)	27.84(31.79)	1200.00
9	Control	14.49(22.37)	51.68(45.96)	708.33
	SEM±	(1.41)	(1.56)	
	CD at 5%	(4.22)	(4.69)	

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